
Thermal Effect and Active Groups Fluctuation in the Process of Spontaneous Combustion in Guzhuang Mine, Shanxi

Jaja Davie¹, Md Jahid Hasan²

¹School of Safety Science and Engineering, Henan Polytechnic University, Jiaozuo, Henan 454000, China

²School of Civil Engineering, Henan Polytechnic University, Jiaozuo, Henan, China

*Corresponding author at: State Key Laboratory Cultivation Base for Gas Geology and Gas Control, Henan Polytechnic University, Jiaozuo 454000, China.

E-mail: daviecjj@gmail.com

Abstract: This study investigates the spontaneous combustion process of long-flame coal sourced from Guzhuang mine in Shanxi Province. Using a C600 high-precision microcalorimeter, gas chromatograph, and Fourier transform infrared spectrometer, the thermal effects, gas products, and functional group changes during coal oxidation were systematically analyzed. Obtained experimental results revealed three distinct stages of thermal effects during coal oxidation: an initial endothermic stage, followed by slow exothermic and rapid exothermic stage. The initial exothermic temperature was observed at 78°C, with the coal oxygen reaction significantly accelerating after 209°C. Carbon monoxide (CO) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) were identified as the primary oxidation products. Particularly, CO concentration increased rapidly above 150°C, establishing it as a reliable indicator gas for monitoring spontaneous combustion. The oxygen consumption rate demonstrated exponential growth with rising temperature. Functional group analysis indicated minimal change in aromatic hydrocarbon content during oxidation. Contrarily, the content of oxygen-containing functional groups increased with temperature. Aliphatic hydrocarbon content initially increased, then stabilized, and afterward decreased. This research clarifies key characteristic parameters across different stages of coal spontaneous combustion, offering a robust theoretical foundation and technical support for early prediction and prevention methods. These findings are crucial for enhancing coal mine safety and productivity.

Keywords: functional group, gas products, long-flame coal, spontaneous combustion.

1. Introduction

Incidents of spontaneous combustion remain prominent, particularly as coal is a leading energy provider [1]. Mine fires pose significant risks, including safety hazards, environmental damage, and economic losses. As of the most recent available data, China, India, and the United States are the world's leading coal consuming countries. However, China remains one of the top countries with high coal consumption rate, according to Statista, China's consumption rate increases yearly and in 2022 it was the largest coal consumer with nearly 55% of the total consumption. China produces approximately 4.8 billion tons of coal per year and around 90-94% of the active mines reported spontaneous combustion [2], [3].

Coal spontaneous combustion is also considered a huge challenge in the coal value chain, and the occurrence of spontaneous combustion is a result of adequate oxygen and heat produced during the low temperature reaction of coal with oxygen if not sufficiently dispatched through conduction or convection leading to accumulation of heat within the coal mass [4], [5]. Under favorable conditions of high heating rate, coal gain thermal runaway and fire ensue [6]. Coal thermal runaway is a violent and uncontrollable exothermic reaction process that occurs when coal is exposed to high temperatures or external heat sources. When the heat accumulation rate exceeds

the heat dissipation rate, temperature continues to rise, and the coal temperature gets out of control and eventually results in coal spontaneous combustion [7]. Spontaneous combustion results in fire and the occurrence basis differs as it can happen during extraction of the coal, at storage and also during transportation. In China approximately 51% of the combustion usually happens in the goaf and also stockpiles [8]. Mechanism of spontaneous combustion is not an obvious incident as it happens slowly and is very hard to identify. It can be concluded that by the time combustion is identified it would already reach a dangerous level and such occurrences need prevention [9].

As coal continues to be the primary energy source for various sectors in China, the depths of working faces and goafs in coal mines also constantly increases. This continual depth naturally means that coal seams remain highly combustible, which has led to extensive research and the implementation of various theories and experimental prevention methods to mitigate mine fires. Among the proposed theories, the coal-oxygen reaction is a widely accepted theory directly linked to coal combustion in mines. This reaction results in mine fires primarily through two related mechanisms which are air leakage into the goaf and followed by oxidation. As the working face advances, creating the goaf, air infiltrates these voids, providing adequate oxygen. Inside the goaf, oxidation of the residual coal occurs at different temperatures and the heat generated by this oxidation, if not effectively dissipated, accumulates and constantly rises the coal's temperature, eventually promoting spontaneous combustion and resulting in mine fires [10].

Through different institutes, numerous experiments have been conducted to study spontaneous combustion and formulate measures to prevent coal combustion. These experiments include medium to high scale tests [5]. Pan R *et al.* investigated the process of coal oxidation and spontaneous combustion by using high precision Calorimeter and X-ray diffractometer. After a series of recorded coal oxidation experiments, it was concluded that coal spontaneous combustion consists of 4 obvious segmentation characteristics which are heat absorption stage (stage I), slow exothermic phase (stage II), accelerated heat release phase (stage III) and continuous exothermic phase (stage IV) [11]. Wang *et al.* investigated the risks of coal combustion on 5 different samples, and the summarized results indicated an increase on the oxygen consumption rate in stages II and III due to increasing temperatures which accelerated the oxidation rate [12]. Under different oxygen concentration, Yutao Z *et al.* analyzed its effects during the coal exothermic reaction process and the obtained results showed that heat release of coal oxidation declined with the decrease of oxygen concentration. The reduction of oxygen concentration could be used to suppress coal combustion [13].

To detect coal combustion at an early stage, mines have adopted the gas analysis method to track coal self-ignition and monitor any emergence or shifts in concentration of specific gaseous byproducts during coal oxidation [14]. Wen H *et al.* compared two methods of coal spontaneous combustion characterization parameters testing by using coal spontaneous combustion test bench and the isothermal difference-led test system. The analyzed results showed the ZXYM adiabatic spontaneous combustion period was 204.7 h and ZXDY adiabatic spontaneous combustion period was 233.4 h. Furthermore, the results exhibited two different critical temperatures (heat release), ZXYM was (60 ~ 70 °C) and ZXDY was 61.9 °C, both experiments showed that CO gas concentration increased with the increase of coal sample oxidation temperature [15]. Wang K *et al.* also used a temperature-programmed heating experiment to study coal with different oxygen concentration and different gaseous compounds were analyzed, including O₂, CO and CO₂. The results showed that pre-heated coal samples at 80 °C led to minimum oxygen consumption rate and minimum concentration of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and carbon monoxide (CO) [16]. To provide information for understanding combustion and implement some idea to prevent it, Yan H *et al.* conducted an experimental investigation using oxygen concentrations of 21%, 15%, 10% and 5% on 2 coal samples to analyze oxidation products, oxygen consumption rate, production rate of CO and CO₂ and heat release intensity. Results obtained displayed that when there is higher oxygen concentration, there is also high (CO, CO₂) generated [17].

Mao *et al.* carried out an experiment to study the characteristics of coal combustion by using XK-III apparatus and storing 1500kg coal sample for 39 days. The results showed an increase in temperature after 30 days when it reached 60 °C, which led to heating rate increase from 0.4 °C/h to 2.5 °C/h. This also led to high oxygen consumption and generation of CO and CO₂ respectively [18]. Zhang *et al.* conducted an experiment using samples from Yangdong wellfield of Jizhong Energy to study mechanism of coal spontaneous combustion and obtained results highlighted intense oxidation at low temperatures and when the air supply was 120 ml/min, at

the same air supply CO generation rate and heat release was also intense [19]. Lu *et al.* carried out an experiment on raw and water-soaked coal samples, they discovered the increase in CO and CO₂ concentrations was co-related to the increase in temperature. They labelled CO and CO₂ to be important gasses which are directly related to the coal spontaneous combustion mechanism [20]. Yang Y *et al.* used coal spontaneous combustion experiment platform to obtain heating rate, oxygen consumption rate, gas generation rate, single gas and composite gas index, they found out that CO/CO₂ concentration increased from 30 °C [21].

The reaction between coal and active functional groups has been documented to be closely linked to coal spontaneous combustion [22]. As oxygen interact with the coal's molecular structure, chemical bonds with active functional groups are formed and this is considered as an exothermic reaction.

Although there are numerous researches into coal spontaneous combustion, there is a lack of sufficient and precise data to comprehensively articulate the key macroscopic and microscopic changes that occur throughout the entire coal-oxygen reaction process. This study seeks to bridge that significant gap by using a C600 high-precision microcalorimeter and gas chromatography analyzer to improve the accuracy and sensitivity of the experiment. In addition, collected data is analyzed in an understandable manner to give explanatory of the intensity of coal combustion at each stage. Thermal effect, O₂ concentration, generated gasses and main functional groups are analyzed. The results from this paper provides theoretical basis for the prevention of spontaneous combustion and these findings can be used by coal mines susceptible to fires to prevent devastating outcomes. Earlier detection will save environmental and economic damages.

2. Experimental Materials and Methods

Coal sample collection and screening

Raw coal samples for this experiment were collected from Guzhuang Mine which is located in Shanxi Province, China. This mine is susceptible to spontaneous combustion and the sample collected is long flame coal, the coal was retrieved from an operating seam to make sure fresh coal was collected. The selected large lumps were checked for any cracks or abnormalities before being wrapped in preservative packaging and transported to the laboratory for further screening. After the coal reached the laboratory, it was further crashed into fine coal using a crusher and screened into 5 different coal samples as shown in *Figure 1*. Particle sizes ranging from 0-10mm were obtained and each particle size measuring 20g was taken and mixed for experimental (see Table 1).

Figure 1: Coal sample collection and screening

Table 1: Particle size and Sample

Particle size (mm)	0-2	2-4	4-6	6-8	8-10
Sample (g)	20	20	20	20	20

The recorded physical analysis of the retrieved coal samples included: ash content, moisture, volatile matter and fixed carbon (see Table 2).

Table 2: Industrial analysis of Coal samples

Coal sample (%)	Ash content	Moisture	Volatile matter	Fixed carbon
Guzhuang coal sample	18.81	0.96	11.15	69.08

Experimental equipment

To study the heat release intensity during the simulated heating process a C600 high-precision microcalorimeter was used as shown in *Figure 2*. It is equipped with precision of $\pm 2\%$; sensitivity of $6 \mu\text{v/mW}$ and resolution of 0.5 mW . The calorimeter's precision range of $\pm 2\%$ ensured the data's validity and the margin error didn't affect the analyses. During the experiment, real-time temperature and heat flow data were simultaneously transferred to the computer. Using the C600 equipment, parameter changes such as heat flow, heat flow increase, initial heat release, and maximum heat flow were obtained and analyzed.

Figure 2: C600 microcalorimeter

To study the gaseous byproducts generated during coal oxidation, the gas chromatograph was used as shown in *Figure 3*. This system is equipped with GC-4000A gas chromatograph, air compressor and hydrogen generator among others. All the controls of this system are operated on a computer. Within the equipment there is temperature control system, that controls the temperature of the injection port, column temperature box, and detector to provide accurate data for the analysis process.

Figure 3: Gas chromatograph

The VERTEX-70V Fourier transform infrared spectrometer from Bruker, Germany was used to analyze main functional groups as shown in *Figure 4*. This advanced instrument boasts a wide spectral range of $7800\text{--}350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, a high resolution better than 0.2 cm^{-1} , and a wavenumber accuracy superior to 0.005 cm^{-1} . With a signal to

noise ratio exceeding 55000:1, it enables high resolution, real time in-situ scanning of coal samples within the reaction tank during heating, providing absorbance data of micro active groups.

Figure 4: VERTEX-70V Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer

3. Results & Discussion

Characteristics of thermal effect during coal oxidation

Heat flow is defined as thermal energy transfer which is heat passing through a cross section in a unit of time. The dHF (differential heat flow) curve is calculated by differentiating heat flow data with respect to time. It represents the rate at which heat flow changes, effectively showing the acceleration of heat release. As a result from the coal oxidation experiment, illustration in Figure 5 displays the heat flow and dHF curve obtained from the experiment.

Figure 5: Heat flow and dHF curve

From the research and analysis of the obtained experimental data, the heat flow of the tested coal samples shows negative value at the beginning of the experiment and this is because in the early stage of coal's low-temperature oxidation, moisture evaporates and absorbs heat, while the heat released is generated by physical adsorption, resulting in relatively low heat release. As the temperature continued to rise, the sample experience its first initial exothermic at 78 °C and this is because of the chemical adsorption which gradually intensifies resulting in more heat release than physical adsorption. When the temperature reached approximately 209 °C, heat flow accelerated exponentially. In addition, as coal oxidized, the continuous consumption and formation of different functional groups in influenced the heat flow trend. The obtained data of the dHF curve shows a similar trend of first negative value and gradually rising as temperature increased. At 78 °C the coal experiences an equilibrium stage of heat absorption and heat release. The dHF curve reached its highest peak at approximately 250 °C and

this is due to the chemical bonds and functional groups which are more active during high temperatures, resulting in accelerated coal-oxygen recombination reaction.

During the programmed temperature coal oxidation experiment, the research shows heat flow evolution, particularly from two distinct characteristic temperature points which are 30 - 300 °C range. These points are effectively divided into 3 stages as illustrated below in *Figure 6*.

Figure 6: Divided 3 stages of thermal effect

1st Stage is the starting point of the experiment and from 30 °C as the reaction progresses, the heat flow gradually depletes to a minimum value around -40 (mW) with increasing temperature. As the heat flow hits the minimum value, the dHF curve reaches 0 (mJ) which shows that the exothermic and endothermic are at an equilibrium point. In this case when the equilibrium point is reached, 78 °C can be identified as the initial heat release temperature of the reaction. The reason for the 1st stage heat flow curve depletion is that during the initial heating stage, the moisture present in the coal evaporates, absorbing a significant amount of heat, as a result the heat flow value shows a decreasing trend at the beginning of the reaction. This is commonly identified as macroscopic to an endothermic process, which is typical of the initial stage in coal's low temperature oxidation and within this stage coal porous structure physically and chemically adsorbs oxygen molecules onto its surface, however heat release amount is small and the process is also slow. When the temperature exceeds 78 °C, the coal sample's heat release rate progressively surpassed its heat absorption rate, causing the heat flow curve to rise. As the heat flow curve rose, the heat flow value showed a gradual increase. When the temperature exceeded 78 °C, now the coal started to experience slow exothermic and this phase is referred as 2nd stage. At this stage the coal oxygen reaction is slightly slow and the chemical bonds within the coal structure start to break, creating free radicals which are highly reactive accelerating the exothermic reaction which manifest in the later stage. As the temperature continues to increase, the coal reaches a point where the heat release rate is greater than 0 (mW), the heat release is greater than the heat absorption. This happens when the temperature hits approximately 209 °C and this phase is referred as the 3rd Stage. Finally, the coal oxygen reaction is faster and critical temperature is reached, at this point heat generation can no longer be dissipated by conduction or convection resulting in coal ignition and thermal runaway.

Characteristics of gasses indicator during coal oxidation

The programmed temperature experimental was set from 30 – 300 °C and as the experiment was being conducted, gaseous byproducts produced at different temperatures were obtained and analyzed using a gas chromatograph. During coal oxidation, coal reacts with oxygen and three processes are realized, which are physical adsorption, chemical adsorption, and oxidation reactions. Each stage produces different amounts and types of gaseous byproducts. Collected experimental results showed that CO and CO₂ are the main gaseous products of coal oxidation. Among these, CO is continuously generated across all stages of the oxidation process, establishing it as a reliable indicator gas for monitoring coal spontaneous combustion. Furthermore, since oxygen (O₂) is essential for coal-oxygen reactions, its concentration changes significantly influencing the

process and it should be analyzed. To study the characteristic of gasses indicator during coal oxidation, the study analysed key gasses such as oxygen concentration rate and the production of indicator gas concentrations.

Oxygen concentration rate

Oxygen is one of the three macroscopic essential elements for coal spontaneous combustion and plays a crucial role in the process. The concentration of oxygen directly influences the rate of the coal oxygen reaction. In programmed temperature oxidation experiments, the difference in oxygen concentration between the inlet and outlet reflects the amount of oxygen consumed. A lower outlet concentration indicates greater oxygen consumption and a more intense coal-oxygen reaction. Equation for O_2 consumption is:

$$V_{O_2}(T) = \frac{Q \cdot c_{O_2}^1}{S \cdot L} \cdot \ln \frac{c_{O_2}^1}{c_{O_2}^2} \quad (1)$$

In the formula:

$V_{O_2}(T)$ -Rate of oxygen consumption by the coal sample, mol/s, mol/(cm³ .S

Q-Air or gas supply volume/flow rate (mL/min); S = Bottom area of the coal sample chamber ,cm²;

L = The height of the coal sample chamber, cm;

$c_{O_2}^1$ -Oxygen concentration at the inlet ,%;

$c_{O_2}^2$ - Oxygen concentration at the outlet ,%.

Figure 7: Oxygen Consumption rate

During the coal oxygen reaction process, heat accumulates as a result of multiple actions including physical adsorption, chemical adsorption, and chemical reaction of coal samples. The outcome can be observed through oxygen concentration depletion. Mostly the oxygen consumption rate of coal is influenced by factors such as oxygen concentration and air flow rate. The rate of oxygen consumption directly reflects the intensity of the oxidation reaction. As illustrated in *Figure 7*, the oxygen consumption rate of coal shows an exponential growth trend with increasing temperature during coal oxidation experiment. This accelerated oxygen consumption is a result of thermal transition from physical adsorption to chemical reactions, where pyrolysis generates more oxygen consuming functional groups and reactive radicals that drive the oxidation process.

CO and CO₂ gas concentration

The primary macroscopic characteristics of coal oxidation reactions are heat release and gas production, among the produced gases CO is predominantly produced through oxidation and pyrolysis, with minimal amounts naturally present in coal. CO₂ is released not only from oxidation and pyrolysis but also from the thermal decomposition of the already existing oxides in coal, resulting in significantly higher quantities. CO₂ can be detected even in the initial stages of the reaction. As a result, CO and CO₂ are commonly used as indicator gases to monitor and assess coal oxidation process. As the temperature increased, CO and CO₂ were constantly produced and released as exhibited in *Figure 8*:

Figure 8: CO and CO₂ Concentration

From Figure 8, it can be observed that during the initial oxidation stage, the amount of CO produced from coal sample increased gradually with rising temperature and the concentration could be divided into slow and rapid concentration. In the early stage of oxidation (below 150°C), the CO concentration increased slowly, following an approximately linear trend. Beyond 150 °C, the CO concentration rose rapidly, showing exponential growth in the later stages of the reaction. The CO concentration curve demonstrates exponential growth with increasing temperature, where the inflection point corresponds to accelerated oxidation rates and transition to active combustion phases. It can also be concluded that during high production of CO, a large number of active functional groups were consumed. In the initial stage of coal oxidation, the samples became loose, which increased the specific surface area in contact with oxygen and as a result, the CO concentration rate grew rapidly in the later stage. On the other hand, CO₂ can be detected at the initial stage of the experiment because it is readily adsorbed onto coal surfaces and at ambient temperatures carboxyl group are quickly decomposed releasing CO₂. As shown in the above illustration, from the initial oxidation there is a gradual increase in CO₂ concentration with rising temperature which is a sign of combustion intensity at each stage. This reflected that temperature plays a crucial role in affecting the concentration of CO and CO₂, detecting these gasses early can help to stop combustion at an early stage.

Characteristics of functional groups during coal oxidation

Coal is a complex macromolecular substance. After oxidation, the number and type of its functional groups will change. A FTIR infrared spectroscopy equipment was used to analyze the changes in the content of microscopic active groups in coal molecules to determine the oxidation characteristics of coal and analyze coal combustion characteristics on a microscopic perspective.

The complex macromolecular structure of coal results in an infrared spectroscopy displayed various peaks, each representing a different functional group. Based on established research into coal's microstructure, key characteristic peaks corresponded to hydroxyl, aliphatic, aromatic, and various oxygen-containing functional groups. Analyzing these peaks allows a deeper understanding of coal's structural properties. The processed infrared spectroscopy is presented in Figure 9 below:

Figure 9: Infrared spectroscopy

The FTIR spectrum was divided into three band peaks, the 2800-3000 cm^{-1} presented: aliphatic Hydrocarbon, 1400-1800 cm^{-1} presented: Oxygen-containing functional groups and 700-900 cm^{-1} presented: Aromatic hydrocarbons.

Aromatic hydrocarbons, which are abundant and structurally stable components of coal molecules, showed characteristic spectral peaks in the infrared region. By exploring the changing trend of aromatic hydrocarbon content at different temperatures, it is of reference significance to verify the changing rules of oxygen-containing functional groups and aliphatic hydrocarbon content. These included the stretching vibrations of aromatic C-H bonds (3272-3061 cm^{-1}), the bending vibrations of various substituted aromatic hydrocarbons (900-700 cm^{-1}), and the C=C skeletal stretching vibrations within the aromatic ring (1604-1599 cm^{-1}). Furthermore, the spectral data within the 700-900 cm^{-1} range primarily reflected the degree of condensation of aromatic nuclei. To analyze the fitted data, the area of each individual peak within this region was calculated. These peak areas were summed to determine the total area change of aromatic substituted hydrocarbons in the 700-900 cm^{-1} region as a function of increasing temperature. Figure 10 shows the infrared peak fitting for aromatic hydrocarbons in coal samples.

Figure 10: Aromatic hydrocarbons peaks

As shown in Figure 11 with the increase of in-situ temperature, the aromatic hydrocarbon content in coal gradually decreased. However, this fluctuation is minor throughout the coal oxidation reaction, indicating that the reaction primarily involves the side chains of macromolecular structures, while the aromatic nuclei remain largely unaffected. The result suggest that aromatic compound's influence in the coal-oxygen reaction is minimum.

Figure 11: Aromatic hydrocarbon content

Oxygen plays a crucial role in the spontaneous combustion of coal, and the intensity of the coal-oxygen reaction is directly reflected in the formation and transformation of oxygen-containing functional groups. The microstructure of these oxygen-containing functional groups is characterized by specific infrared spectral peaks, including carbonyl stretching vibrations from aldehydes, ketones, and carboxylic acids ($1754\text{-}1678\text{ cm}^{-1}$), C-O stretching vibrations found in phenols, alcohols, ethers, and esters ($1198\text{-}962\text{ cm}^{-1}$), carboxyl stretching vibrations ($2880\text{-}2818\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and aliphatic ether stretching vibrations ($1483\text{-}1347\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The illustrated diagram of the peak fitting of these primary oxygen-containing functional groups in coal samples is presented in *Figure 12*.

Figure 12: Oxygen-containing functional groups peaks

As shown below in *Figure 13*, the diagram demonstrates an increasing trend in the content of carbon oxygen functional groups within coal as temperature increased. The rapid high activity of these groups makes them highly susceptible to reaction with oxygen. This exothermic reaction releases significant heat, which in turn accelerates the spontaneous combustion process of coal. Therefore, the higher the content of carbon oxygen groups in coal, the higher the tendency of coal to self-ignite.

Figure 13: Carbon oxygen functional groups content

Aliphatic hydrocarbons are considered highly active functional groups in coal. Their side chains and bridging bonds are readily attacked and broken by oxygen atoms, which releases heat. Specifically, the $-\text{CH}_3$ and $-\text{CH}_2-$ groups within these hydrocarbons are key participants in coal-oxygen reactions and play a crucial role. Aliphatic hydrocarbons exist in coal molecules primarily as methylene ($-\text{CH}_2-$) and methyl ($-\text{CH}_3$) groups. Their main

spectral peaks include symmetric methylene stretching vibration around 2855 cm^{-1} , symmetric methyl stretching vibration around 2875 cm^{-1} , antisymmetric methylene stretching vibration around 2925 cm^{-1} and antisymmetric methyl stretching vibration around 2975 cm^{-1} . The fitted spectra of the aliphatic hydrocarbon peaks for the coal sample are shown in the Figure below:

Figure 14: Aliphatic hydrocarbon peaks

As shown in Figure 15 with the increase of in-situ temperature, the content of aliphatic hydrocarbons in coal shows a three-stage trend which are initial increase, stabilization, and a continuous decrease. During the initial increase and stabilization stage, the long-chain aliphatic hydrocarbons within the coal undergo thermal cracking, producing smaller hydrocarbon molecules. This fragmentation leads to the observed gradual increase in aliphatic hydrocarbon content during this phase. As the reaction progressed, the rate of aliphatic hydrocarbon consumption began to increase significantly, contributing to their later stabilization before a decline. In addition, under high temperature conditions, aliphatic hydrocarbon groups become highly reactive in the coal oxygen reaction, indicating a more intense reaction process. This rapid reactivity at high temperatures significantly contributes to the accelerated decrease in their content as observed in the final stage.

Figure 15: Aliphatic hydrocarbons content

4. Conclusion

This paper conducts experimental research on the oxidation characteristics of coal, with the coal samples collected from Guzhuang Coal Mine in Shanxi Province. The study explores the oxidation characteristics of coal

from both macroscopic and microscopic perspectives: the macroscopic aspect covers the patterns of thermal effects (endothermic and exothermic processes), oxygen consumption rate, and the generation of gaseous products (carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide); the microscopic aspect focuses on the peak position changes and content evolution features of the main functional groups. The programmed temperature experiment is set within a temperature range of 30 - 300°C, aiming to analyze the changes in oxygen consumption rate, gaseous products, and the peak positions of aliphatic, aromatic, and various oxygen-containing functional groups during the coal oxidation process. Additionally, this paper discusses the initial exothermic stage and the thermal runaway stage. The main research results are as follows:

The experiment clearly defines the patterns of thermal effect changes during the coal oxidation process, dividing it into three distinct stages: the initial endothermic stage, the slow exothermic stage, and the rapid exothermic stage. It has been determined that the initial exothermic temperature is 78°C, and when the temperature exceeds 209°C, the coal-oxygen reaction significantly accelerates, entering the rapid exothermic stage.

The oxygen consumption rate shows an increasing trend with the rise in temperature, a phenomenon that confirms the crucial role of oxygen in the coal oxidation process. The continuous consumption of oxygen prompts other functional groups to continuously participate in the reaction. The carbon monoxide content gradually increases with the temperature rise, and when the temperature exceeds 150°C, its content shows a rapid growth trend; while carbon dioxide exhibits a high concentration at the initial stage of the experiment and continues to increase with the temperature rise.

The analysis results of aliphatic, aromatic, and various oxygen-containing functional groups show that within the wavelength range of 700 - 900 cm^{-1} , the peak positions of aromatic hydrocarbons fluctuate, and the content of aromatic hydrocarbons in coal gradually decreases, resulting in the minimal impact on the coal-oxygen reaction. The content of carbon-oxygen functional groups increases with the temperature rise and shows high reactivity in the coal-oxygen reaction, significantly accelerating the combustion process; the content of aliphatic hydrocarbons experiences three stages: initial increase, stable maintenance, and continuous decrease.

Acknowledgements

Projects funded by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 52174169); Projects funded by the Outstanding Youth Fund of Henan Province (No. 232300421015).

Declaration of Interest Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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